

A STUDY ON SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES WITH THEIR WORKING ENVIRONMENT AT TANEJA AEROSPACE AND AVIATION LIMITED, HOSUR

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Abstract

Conducting study on comfortable environment is an attempt to understand and predict the mentality of employees at their work place. The environment has been considered as one of the important factor for carrying out the work in peaceful manner. Now a day's environment plays an important role in the output given by the employees. The Government has played an increasing role in employer-employee relations in part by becoming the biggest employer and partly by regulating working conditions in the private sector. The Government of India has enacted procedural as well substantive laws to regulate employer-employee relations in the country. This article helps us to understand the comfortable environment provided by employers to their employees atTaneja Aerospace And Aviation Limited, Hosur.

Key Words:Comfort, Employees, Employers, Environment, Satisfaction, Socio-Economic Characteristics

1. Introduction

Employer refers to a legal entity that controls and directs a servant or worker under an express or implied contract of employment and pays (or it obligated to pay) him or her salary or wages in compensation. Employers try to gain loyalty of workers in various ways. They are concerned mainly with imposing motivation, commitment and efficiency of labour. Employers negotiate individually as well as through their associations with employees' representatives to settle terms and conditions of employment. Some employers share decision-making power with workers.

Employee refers to an individual who works part-time or full time under a contract of employment, whether oral or written, express or implied, and has recognized rights and duties. Considering the competitive nature of industries and technological advancement, the importance of employer-employee relationship becomes more critical reason being that to meet constant changing needs of employees. Effective human resource management becomes very crucial in achieving business success. The greatest asset of an organization is

considered to be the Human Resource and the greatest challenge of an organization is how to manage these human resources efficiently and effectively so as to achieve set objectives of the organization. In order to find out the satisfaction level of employees with the working environment in Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Limited this study has been undertaken.

2. About Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Limited

Manufacturing business was evolved from the initial business of this company that was to manufacture the Partenavia P68C, six seat, and twin-engine aircraft in India (That was the first and only private sector company in India to build). Then currently they are manufacturing aero structures for Hindustan Aeronautics Limited (HAL), Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), National Aerospace Laboratories (NAL), Aeronautical Development Establishment (ADE), and Number of modifications on Indian Navy and Air force Helicopters and Aircraft. Of these, the largest structures that they manufacture are for ISRO where they build most of the structural assemblies for the Booster rockets of the GSLV program. They have also built major structures of 14 seat Saras aircraft developed by NAL. This is the largest dedicated private sector aero structure manufacturer in India.

3. Statement of the Problem

As the employees are one of the important factors of production, the success and outcome of the business are depend upon the satisfaction and performance of the employees. Employees can give maximum output only when they have comfortable and pleasant environment. Employer is the responsible person to create a good environment to their employees. For that purpose the question, “whether the employees are having the comfortable environment at their work place or not?” has to be answered. In this study the effort is taken to find answer to this question.

4. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to find the satisfaction level of employees with their working environment provided by Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Limited. And also to analyse the relationship between the socio-economic characteristics and satisfaction level of employees at Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Limited.

5. Hypothesis of the Study

The physical layout of the office is important to maximizing productivity. People need enough room to work, the correct supplies/materials, and a

comfortable and pleasant environment. The employer should make sure that all equipments are designed so that they positively motivate workers by helping them with their needs to do the work. The comfortable environment will differ from person to person. Based on the place and nature of job their environment differs. They also depend on their attitude, preference, satisfaction, feelings, etc. In order to find the factor which affects the satisfaction level of employees with their working environment the following null hypothesis is framed.

H₀: The satisfaction level of employees with their working environment and their socio-economic characteristics are independent.

6. Methodology and Tools

This study is an empirical research. Survey method is adopted for this study. Primary data were collected directly from the employees by interviewing them personally. Interview schedule is prepared as two parts. In the first part of the interview schedule, the socio-economic characteristics of the employees are asked i.e., age, gender, educational status, department, designation, salary scale, and experience. The second part of the interview schedule deals with the working environment provided to employees. In this part twelve statements were given about their working environment. These twelve statements have been categorized into three scales namely satisfied or moderate or dissatisfied with the provided working environment. If an employee is satisfied with given environment then 3 points has been allotted, if he agrees moderate then he is allotted the score of 2 points or else the score is 1. After providing the points to all the statements, the scores of each employee have been totaled. As per this calculation an employee can score maximum of 36 (12 X 3) and minimum of 12 (12 X 1). The employees who are scored from 12 to 19 are considered as they are dissatisfied with their provided environment. Scores from 20 to 28 are considered as moderate. Scores from 29 to 36 are considered as satisfied with their working environment. After the scores are calculated the tables were prepared and analyzed with the help of chi square test.

7. Sampling Design

The Taneja Aerospace And Aviation Limited consists of 500 employees. Among that 200 sample employees are selected on the basis of random sampling method. These sample employees are the representatives of the population of this study.

8. Limitation of the Study

The study has certain limitations

1. As the time and resources are limited, all the employees of Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Limited could not be studied for this research purpose.
2. Another limitation is that the employee might be reluctant to disclose some information about their employers which might affect the reliability of the research.

9. Analysis

The satisfaction levels of employees of Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Limited with their working environment are given in the Table 1 and Chart 1.

TABLE 1: SATISFACTION WITH WORKING ENVIRONMENT OF EMPLOYEES

S.NO	Environment at working place	No. of employees	Percentage of employees
1	Satisfied	127	63.50
2	Moderate	58	29.00
3	Not Satisfied	15	7.50
Total		200	100

Table 1 and chart 1 shows that out of 200(100%) employees 127(63.5%) employees have been satisfied with the environment provided by employer, 58(29%) employees have been moderately satisfied with the environment provided by employer whereas the remaining employees are not satisfied with the environment provided by employer.

SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES WITH WORKING ENVIRONMENT AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF EMPLOYEES

Socio economic characteristics of the employees include age,gender,educational status, occupation, department,designation salary scale and experience. These characteristics of the employees may or may not influence the satisfaction level of the employees with their working environment. In order to find the relationship between satisfaction level of employees with the provided working environment and socio-economic characteristics of the employees, the following hypothesis has been framed.

H₀: Satisfaction of employees with their working environment & socio economic characteristics are independent.

It is statistically analyzed with the help of chi-square test at 5% level of significance and the results are given as follows.

$\chi^2 = 4.584$

Table Value = 9.48

Degree of freedom = 4

From the above analysis it can be concluded that the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. Hence the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between the satisfaction of employees with the working environment and their age.

$\chi^2=1.925$

Table Value =5.99

Degree of freedom = 2

The above analysis shows that the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. Hence it is concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between gender and the satisfaction of employees with the working environment provided by employer.

$\chi^2=6.439$

Table Value =5.99

Degree of freedom = 2

The above analysis shows that the calculated value of χ^2 is more than the table value. Hence it is concluded that the framed null hypothesis is rejected and there is relationship between educational status and the satisfaction of employees with the working environment provided by the employer.

$\chi^2 = 5.391$

Table Value = 12.591 Degree of freedom = 6

The above analysis shows that the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. Hence it is concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between department in which the employees are working and the satisfaction of employees with the working environment provided by employer.

$\chi^2 = 9.108$ Table Value =9.48 Degree of freedom = 4

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value in the above analysis. Hence it is concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between designation of the employees and the satisfaction of employees with the working environment provided by employer.

$\chi^2 = 3.046$ Table Value =9.48 Degree of freedom = 4

The above analysis shows that the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. Hence it is concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between salary scale and the satisfaction of employees with their working environment.

$\chi^2 = 0.962$

Table Value = 9.48

Degree of freedom = 4

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value in the above analysis. Hence it is concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between experience and the satisfaction of employees with the working environment provided by employer.

10. Conclusion

This study shows that out of 200 employees, 127 employees are satisfied with their working environment, 58 employees are moderately satisfied and the remaining 15 employees are not satisfied with the working environment provided by employer. The entire socio economic characteristics (age, gender, educational status, department, designation, salary scale and experience) of the employees have been tested with the satisfaction level of employees with their working environment by using chi-square test at 5% level of significance. From this study it can be concluded that except educational qualification of the employees all other socio economic characteristics of the employees have no relationship with the satisfaction level of employees with the working environment.

References

1. A Textbook of Human Resource Management, R S Dwivedi
2. Human Resource Management, SeemaSanghi
3. Managing Human Resources, J P Mahajan
4. Human Resource Management: Text & Cases, Sharon Pande & Swapnalekha Basak
5. Human Resource Management, V S P Rao